

CALCULATION OF A ROAD MILLING TOOTH BY THE METHOD OF FINITE ELEMENTS

Mahammadjonov Nurmuhammad¹

¹assistant of Andijan machine building institute;

Mamasoliyev Bunyodbek²

²assistant of Andijan machine building institute.

Muxtorov Sarvarbek³

³student of Andijan machine building institute.

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We will transfer our model, which we designed the simplified road milling tooth using the Solid Edge V20 program, to the ANSYS program[1].

Figure 1. Road milling tooth hard edge model in V20 application.

It will be necessary to distinguish the model created according to the theory of finite elements with finite elements.

The Ansys 15.0 program has 5 types of allocation to finite elements (ChEA).[2,3].

1. Automatic

2. Tetrahedrons

3. Hex Dominant

4. Sweep

5. MultiZone

Allocation to finite elements in ANSYS 15.0 program (ChEA)

5 types of

In the details ChEA, it is first necessary that we determine the type of element. When choosing the type of Element, the condition of the detailed form that we want to calculate and of course the question posed (stretch, bend, load constancy, model taxlil, etc.k.) required to be considered. As an example, it would be appropriate for us to use the type of road milling tooth in ChEA [Tetrahedrons]. Because the road milling tooth has cylindrical and complex surface parts [4,5,6,7].

According to the condition of the issue given and the assignment being carried out, the most correct way to divide the frezasu tooth in ChEA is to divide it into cubes. If the path milling tooth is broken down into tetrahedron elements, the error of our account results will be large. If we choose the type [Automatic] or [MultiZone], then the path milling tooth is divided into a cubic element type. However, it should be noted that if we use the [Automatic] type, then the ANSYS 15.0 program itself automatically selects the type of element depending on the structure and shape of the detail. And this may not always be the most correct way. It will be appropriate to choose the type of element in the ChEA of details of a complex shape [8,9,10,11]. After all the boundary conditions and

circumstances have been introduced into the path milling tooth, the calculation process is carried out in the finite element method (ChEU) [12].

Figure 2. Road milling tooth using ANSYS program results of separation and calculation of finite elements.

Voltage (Stress) indicates the stresses generated by the static and dynamic forces of the model and their distribution. In this case, based on the operating conditions of the model, the voltage and voltage (Stress) discharge formed under the influence of forces is carried out on it.

It is possible to know what the voltage is in the surfaces of the road milling tooth, through the colors highlighted in it. As a result of the calculation of the road milling tooth presented above, the voltage on the surface of the road milling tooth is changing from $3,5678 \text{ E}+005 \text{ Pa}$ to $7,815 \text{ e}+007 \text{ Pa}$. From this, the surfaces of the road milling tooth separated by a red color have the highest voltage of $7,815 \text{ e}+007 \text{ PA}$. From the highlighted colors, we know that the greatest tension was reflected on the two fixed sides of the track milling tooth. [13,14,15,].

In addition, it is possible to cite the results of the calculation of the speed of the road milling tooth by the following factors.

Displacement (Displacement) indicates the displacement (folding or stretching) of the finite elements that make it up under the influence of a given force of the model being tested.

The reliability coefficient (Factor of Safety) shows the reliability (durability) of the model as a result of the Force (forces) exerted on it, divided into sector. [16,17,18,19]. The road milling tooth is made up of several parts, which are a dental caliper, a cutter body, a puck, a bushing, a handle, a counter-nut, a block, each designed in a separate file.

The method of finite elements (ChEU) is applied to solving many problems in a numerical way, for example, in the design of various mechanical structures, on the board of thermal and fluid flows (complex physical processes), on the observation of chemical processes, electromagnetism, etc.k. very widely used in

pots. Through this practical training, Cheu is limited only to the application of simple construction or detail in matters of bending, bending and compression under the action of external forces. [20,21,22,23].

In many cases, an optional detail or a prototype of a structure is created and checked before it is produced. If some defectors or defects are found in the inspection, they are eliminated and the prototype is re-created and checked again. This is a different approach to the usual methods – finite elements with a thimble (edge). The edge indicates the reaction of the detail or structure being created to external forces or external influences. The edge at detail or construction is divided into small (finite) regions (elements). Each element is:

- Mathematical expression of a discrete part of a physical structure;
- Has a certain displacement and movement.

The foreign method has a number of advantages and amenities, namely:

- Can display the physical motion of the detail or structure being created in virtual conditions;
- Reduction in the number of prototypes of detail or constriction leads to a sharp saving of time and money spent on the development of a new product;
- Optimizes the detail construction being created [24,25,26,27].

In ChEU, you do not need a model that exactly matches the geometry of the detail or structure being designed, but simply create a model that can record its mathematical model based on the given boundary conditions. ChEU has the following advantages and amenities compared to a number of other methods:

1. Through ChEU there is the possibility of calculating details and construcas in geometry that are complex and complex and have boundary conditions (boundary conditions);
2. It is convenient to create and manage single software codes that are common to several types of issues.
3. There are now a lot of verified and user-friendly software codes as well as products.

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